

Enhancing Reading Comprehension Skills of Grade 6 Learners through Project READY PLUS+: An Investigation into Localized Reading Material Efficacy

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ABSTRACT: The study aimed to enhance the reading comprehension level of Grade VI learners during the SY 2023-2024 through the implementation of localized reading materials under Project READY PLUS intervention program. Employing a quasi-experimental design, the study assessed the pre- and post-test scores of 270 Grade six learners, including both the slow and average readers, up to the Third Quarter. The findings revealed a notable improvement in reading levels: the percentage of frustration-level students decreased by 12%, instructional-level students by 8%, and there was an increase of 80 independent readers. Overall, there was a 30% rise in the number of independent readers. The significant improvement in pre- and post-test scores, evidenced by a t-value of -29.185, confirmed the effectiveness of the intervention program Project READY PLUS+. These results highlight the positive impact of using localized reading materials to improve learners' reading comprehension skills, suggesting that tailored content can effectively address specific educational needs and contribute to better learning outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Project READY PLUS, localized reading materials, slow readers, intervention program

INTRODUCTION

Reading has received a lot of attention in the Philippines ever since, mostly because of the public release of Philippine school children's national and international performance exam scores. Thus, learning to read, as defined by [1] Oliveira (2023), has been considered a lifelong process, and as one gets older, so does their capacity for inference. From the first years of elementary school through high school, students' textual complexity—which includes vocabulary, syntactic structuring, and text types—increases gradually, raising the cognitive demands on them. This happens in tandem with students' growth and school advancement, enabling improvements in their teaching and learning processes.

Nonetheless, the Department of Education (DepEd) has made improving people's reading skills one of its top priorities via [2] DepEd Order Number 14, 2018. The campaign, "Every Kid A Reader," aims to make every Filipino child a reader at their grade level by the time they reach fifth grade. Then, during the reading process, elements like feeling, seeing, understanding, applying, and integrating are considered. With this, several reading inventions have been initiated by different public schools to ensure that the goal of the program will be met. However, the Philippines continue to rank at the bottom in Program for International Students Assessment (PISA). Compared to the 2018 result, the country moved up to 75th in the year 2022, but still, it is noticeable that their 2018 scores (549, 518, and 503 respectively) were significantly higher than their 2022 scores (543, 516, and 498 respectively).

To continuously address pressing concerns in the reading comprehension performances of the Filipino learners, just recently, by the virtue of [3] DepEd Memo no. 001 entitled "Implementation of Catch-up Fridays," that was released on January 2024, field officials received orientation and participated in the "Drop Everything and Read" (DEAR) exercise on every Friday in the year 2024. It also served as a forum for field implementers to provide input on the rules governing Catch-up Fridays. A said project aims to improve the fundamental, social, and other pertinent abilities required to carry out the goals of the basic education curriculum. The National Reading and Mathematics Programs, which are essential NLRP subprograms outlined in DO 013, s., are crucial to this project. 2023. In light of these considerations, Lusacan Elementary School (LES) continuously enhance their intervention program – Project READY PLUS. Last School Year (SY), the program mainly used the passages from the Developing Reading Power (DRP), but with last October's pre-test results having hundreds of Grade 6 students fall under Instructional and Frustration Levels, further enhancement of the project is necessary. As a recommendation from the last SY's action research entitled "Project READY+ as Key to Enhancement of Reading Comprehension Skills of Grade 6 Learners," the use of localized reading materials may greatly help the learners become independent readers at the end of the school year.

The overall goal of this study is to support continued efforts to foster a culture of reading enjoyment and improve reading comprehension abilities among all students, especially those in Grade 6.

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I. METHOD

The study's primary objective was to enhance the reading comprehension skills of 270 Grade 6 pupils during the SY 2023-2024. Pretests and posttests were conducted before and after the implementation of the intervention program, which utilized localized reading materials over a six-month period. The study focused not only on slow readers but also on the enhancement of reading comprehension skills for all 270 Grade VI pupils. However, the presented results are limited to the reading progress of the pupils until the Third Quarter of the current school year. Utilizing a quasi-experimental research design, the study involved all Grade 6 students from Lusacan Elementary School who were enrolled during the academic year 2023-2024. The researcher employed purposive sampling, given her role as the English teacher for this grade level. Emphasis was placed on enhancing the reading comprehension skills of learners at this stage, as it is vital for their preparedness to progress to the next level of education.

At the start of the SY 2023–2024, the researcher and all the other advisers of Grade 6 used the Phil IRI evaluation instrument to administer pre-reading tests to their students. They were able to determine which students in each specific class were reading at the instructional, independent, and frustrated levels after combining all the data.

Following the assessment of each student's reading comprehension, the researcher and the participating teachers conducted the study, using the locally tailored reading materials to help the students' reading comprehension skills grow.

Every day in the afternoon, 30 minutes before classes end, there is a reading intervention called Project READY PLUS. Every month, all sixth-grade students participated in an individual oral reading evaluation administered by the English teacher to see whether they were making progress. Additionally, pre-reading assessments were carried out by the school heads in Tiaong District II under the direction of the Public Schools District Superintendent (PSDS) for evaluation and monitoring purposes.

After completing the six-month program, students were given a post-test to see if their reading comprehension skills had significantly improved.

A one-group pre-test-post-test research design was used in the study. [4] Yazon, Callo, and Buenvenida (2019) mentioned this kind of study, which measures the same dependent variable in a single group of subjects both before and after a course of treatment. The purpose of the current study was to determine whether the treatment—localized reading materials—was beneficial in improving the reading comprehension abilities of Grade 6 students. To ensure that every participant might profit from the contents, only one set of participants was used.

For the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data, the study employed the following:

Simple descriptive statistics was used including frequency counting and percentage in determining the reading levels of the students based on their pre- test and post-test results.

Two-tailed T-test was employed in determining the significant difference between the reading levels of the students based on their scores in the pre-test and post-test results.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table I. Reading Comprehension Levels of Grade Six Pupils Before the Intervention

Reading Levels	Number of Pupils	Percentage of Pupils
Frustration	86	32%
Instructional	70	26%
Independent	114	42%
Non-readers	0	0%

The table above indicates that majority or 42% of the pupils are already classified as Independent Readers during the pre-test at the beginning of S.Y. 2023-2024. The fact that there is no non-reader in the said grade level is also a good indicator that the school's reading program was successful in the past years. However, a huge percentage of pupils in the Frustration and Instructional levels are still recorded, which means that there is a need to further enrich the reading program.

In a recently published article in 2022, [5] the University of Utah Reading Clinic mentioned that texts that fall within the category of frustrated reading levels are ones for which the reader lacks sufficient background knowledge on the subject or does not meet the requirements for accuracy and pace of instruction while the instructional reading is when a reader is not autonomous but has sufficient prior knowledge of a subject, is able to retrieve text fast, and makes few or no mistakes. The main goal of the study is to make the learners independent readers which means that they can access text rapidly and with minimal errors, provided they have sufficient basic knowledge on the subject.

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Table II. Reading Comprehension Levels of Grade Six Pupils After the Intervention

Reading Levels	Number of Pupils	Percentage of Pupils
Frustration	27	10%
Instructional	47	18%
Independent	194	72%
Non-readers	0	0%

Table 2 shows the distribution of reading levels among respondents after using the localized reading materials in the implementation of Project READY PLUS. The data reveals a significant improvement in reading levels: the percentage of pupils in the frustration level dropped by 12%, and those in the instructional level decreased by 8%. Notably, eighty students transitioned to the independent reading level. This resulted in a 30% increase in independent readers, rising from 42% to 72%. These improvements can be attributed to the use of localized reading materials, which served as the main reading tool in the school's current reading program.

A separate investigation by [6] Sangria and Reduca (2019) addressed reading comprehension challenges faced by Grade Three students at a frustration level at Bendita Elementary School. They introduced an intervention scheme known as Project DEAR and the 12:30 Reading Habit, aiming to provide increased exposure to reading materials, improve comprehension strategies, and develop reading skills through guided practice, fostering greater independence in reading. Using a pre- experimental design, their study evaluated students' reading capabilities via pre- and post-tests, with data analysis conducted using behavior rating scales, percentages, means, standard deviations, and T-Tests. Their findings showed a significant advancement from frustration to instructional reading levels among 44 Grade 3 students following the intervention. This study underscored the effectiveness of the program in enhancing reading proficiency and comprehension, highlighting its significant role in addressing reading challenges and fostering improved reading abilities.

Both studies underscore that with proper intervention; there is a high success rate in achieving the goals of reading programs. The success of Project READY PLUS at Lusacan Elementary School, similar to Project DEAR at Bendita Elementary School, demonstrates the positive impact that targeted, well-structured reading interventions can have on improving students' reading comprehension and proficiency.

Table III. T-test to Show the Significant Difference Before and After Using the Localized Reading Materials

		Mean	SD	Paired Differences				t	Sig. (2-tailed)
				Mean	SD	95% CI of the Difference			
						Lower	Upper		
Reading Comprehension	Pretest	20.94	8.39	-8.73	4.90	-9.32	-8.14	-29.185	0.000
	Posttest	29.67	7.05						

Legend:

- If p-value (Sig.) < 0.05, then it is statistically significant
- If p-value (Sig.) > 0.05, then it is NOT statistically significant

Table 3 presents the outcome of the t-test comparing pre-test and post-test scores. With a t-value of -29.185, a significant difference is evident between the pre- test and post-test scores, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference on the pre-test and post-test scores in reading comprehension of the Grade 6 students before and after using the localized reading materials. Consequently, the t-test outcome strongly suggests that the use of localized reading materials in the intervention program, Project READY+, effectively improves the reading comprehension skills of the students.

The analysis indicates that the use of localized reading materials effectively improved reading comprehension among Grade 6 learners. The intervention led to a notable increase in the percentage of Independent Readers, from 42% to 72%, and significant reductions in Frustration and Instructional levels. These findings are supported by t-test results showing statistically significant improvement (t = -29.185, p = 0.000), demonstrating the intervention's strong impact on student reading outcomes.

These results align with previous research on the effectiveness of targeted reading interventions. [6] Sangria and Reduca (2019) found that Project DEAR significantly increased reading proficiency among Grade 3 students, while [7] Delamente (2019) reported substantial gains in Grade 5 learners' reading comprehension through sustained silent reading practices (t = -7.133, p = .000; CI = 34.256–61.744). Like these studies, the current research underscores that culturally and contextually relevant instructional materials can enhance comprehension, foster good study habits, and boost engagement.

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Project READY PLUS illustrates the transformative potential of localized reading programs by tailoring materials to students' cultural and contextual backgrounds. Beyond improving reading skills, the program fostered engagement and cultural pride, highlighting the importance of designing instructional content that reflects lived experiences of students. For educators, this emphasizes the value of integrating culturally relevant materials, developing engaging activities, providing professional development, and using robust monitoring systems to sustain literacy improvements. These findings position localized, well-structured interventions as effective models for enhancing student achievement.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

After gathering all the necessary data needed in the study, the researcher arrives at the following conclusions:

1. Prior to the implementation of Project READY PLUS+, a considerable number of Grade 6 learners were classified under the instructional and frustration reading levels, indicating the need for an enhanced and more responsive reading intervention.
2. The use of localized reading materials under Project READY PLUS+ significantly improved learners' reading comprehension, as evidenced by the substantial decrease in frustration and instructional readers and the marked increase in independent readers.
3. The statistically significant difference between pre-test and post-test results, as shown by the computed t-value, confirms the effectiveness of localized reading materials in enhancing Grade 6 learners' reading comprehension skills.
4. The intervention demonstrated that contextualized and culturally relevant reading materials help learners better understand texts, sustain interest, and develop reading independence.
5. Overall, the study concludes that Project READY PLUS+ is an effective and sustainable reading intervention, and integrating localized reading materials can greatly contribute to improved literacy outcomes among elementary learners.

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